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Electronic structure and spin dynamics of the metal-organic-framework kagome spin liquid $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$

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Abstract

The metal-organic-framework (MOF) compound $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ is a small-gap semiconductor containing a kagome lattice of antiferromagnetically coupled $S=1/2$ Cu^{II} spins with exchange coupling of order 2 K. First principles spin-polarized DFT+U electronic structure calculations obtain an in-plane nearest-neighbour exchange coupling that matches experiment. Muon spin relaxation confirms no magnetic ordering down to 50 mK and sees spin fluctuations diffusing on a 2D lattice, consistent with a quantum spin liquid (QSL) ground state. Reduction of the diffusion rate on cooling from the paramagnetic region to the low temperature QSL region is assigned to the effects of quantum entanglement. Combined analysis of the spin diffusion, magnetic susceptibility and specific heat in the QSL region suggests close proximity to a quantum critical point and a large density of low energy spinless electronic excitations. A \mathbb{Z}_2 -linear Dirac model for the spin excitations of the QSL is found to provide the best overall consistency with experiment.

INTRODUCTION

In the study of magnetic frustration, the kagome lattice has attracted particular attention, since it provides the most highly frustrated example of an antiferromagnet (AF) in a two-dimensional geometry. Such frustration combined with the strong quantum fluctuations of a spin $1/2$ magnetic unit is conducive to stabilizing a QSL ground state [1, 2]. This QSL state avoids the symmetry breaking associated with magnetic or valence bond order and has a dynamic and highly quantum-entangled character. Entanglement is the primary QSL feature differentiating it from the high temperature paramagnetic (PM) phase. For candidate QSL systems, some particular experimental challenges are detecting this entanglement and distinguishing the type of QSL from the many theoretical possibilities. We demonstrate here the application of μ SR for probing the degree of entanglement in a recently discovered kagome QSL system and apply the μ SR results, in conjunction with previously reported specific heat and magnetic susceptibility, to determine characteristic parameters describing its QSL state.

The theoretical QSL ground state of the $S=1/2$ Heisenberg AF model on the kagome lattice is still far from clear, despite numerous investigations. Some key questions are whether it is gapped or gapless and whether it has $U(1)$ or Z_2 gauge structure. Exact diagonalisation studies on finite lattices initially set a lower bound for the spin gap at $0.05 J$ [3], but later studies gave a vanishingly small spin gap when extrapolated to the infinite lattice limit [4]. Density matrix renormalisation group studies on cylindrical lattice models initially found gapped states [5–8], but recent progress with the technique has revealed gapless Dirac states [9, 10]. Variational Monte Carlo studies mostly find gapless $U(1)$ Dirac states [11–14], but the latest study [15] finds a Z_2 -linear Dirac state whose fluctuation spectrum is indistinguishable from that of the $U(1)$ Dirac state. Tensor network studies have found either the $U(1)$ Dirac state [16] or alternatively a Z_2 state with a vanishingly small gap [17]. A gapless Z_2 spinon Fermi surface (FS) state has also been found recently using a functional renormalization technique that goes beyond mean-field theory [18].

On the experimental side, the most well-studied example of a kagome QSL to date is $\text{ZnCu}_3(\text{OH})_6\text{Cl}_2$, known as herbertsmithite [19, 20]. Inelastic neutron studies show an excitation continuum that could reflect fractionalised spinons and set an upper limit to the gap of $0.015 J$ [21]. Experimental studies are complicated by a defect spin signal that can

obscure the intrinsic properties of the kagome spins. This is due to site mixing between the Cu sites in the kagome plane and the interplanar Zn sites. These difficulties are illustrated by NMR studies from one group finding a gap of order $0.05 J$ [22], whereas a subsequent NMR study from another group was able to separate intrinsic and extrinsic contributions and find a gapless state [23].

FIG. 1. (a) The HOTP molecule. (b) An effective $S=1/2$ structural building block for the $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ framework consisting of one Cu^{2+} ion plus two oxyphenylene radical ligands, each ligand corresponding to one third of a full HOTP molecule. A working model for the spin state of the structural unit has the radical ligands paired into a singlet state, leaving an unpaired spin $1/2$ on the Cu ion. (c) The resulting $S=1/2$ kagome structure with nearest neighbour exchange coupling J .

Finding kagome systems that avoid the defect spins arising from site mixing would provide a valuable contribution to the field and MOF systems can satisfy this aim. Kagome MOF systems made by combining transition metal M with the trigonal planar molecule hexahydroxytriphenylene (HHTP) were reported by Hmadeh and coworkers [24] for $M =$

Co, Ni, Cu. In the Co and Ni systems, extended $M_2(\text{HHTP})_3$ kagome layers alternate with layers of isolated trinuclear $M_3(\text{HHTP})$ complexes. For the case $M = \text{Cu}$, the whole system adopts the kagome structure [25] and the HHTP molecules are fully deprotonated to form hexaoxytriphenylene (HOTP). The kagome layer structure of the resulting MOF system $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ [26] is shown in Fig.1. The stacking of successive layers was suggested to follow a pattern of alternating small displacements parallel to the layer planes [27].

The electronic and magnetic characteristics of this material were reported recently [28]. Conductivity measurements show semiconducting behaviour with a charge energy gap of 0.34 eV. From fitting the magnetic susceptibility to a high temperature series expansion, the exchange coupling J/k_B was estimated to be 2.0 K. A Curie-Weiss fit of the same data over a wide temperature range gave the Weiss constant $\theta = -3.4$ K. For coordination number $z = 4$, this gives an estimate of the exchange coupling as $J/k_B = 2\theta/z = 1.7$ K, similar to that obtained from the high temperature expansion. No evidence for ordering was observed in measurements taken down to 38 mK and power law behaviour was observed for the non-phonon contribution to the specific heat, as well as the ac susceptibility [28]. These properties are all consistent with a gapless QSL.

In this study we use first principles density functional theory to explore the predicted electronic structure and the exchange coupling and we use muon spin relaxation as a local probe of the magnetic properties down to 50 mK. Spin dynamics is explored via the magnetic field dependence of the muon spin relaxation rate, which provides information about the spectral density of the spin fluctuations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electronic structure from DFT

As noted in the previous section, the stacking of successive layers shows a small displacement parallel to the layer planes, suggesting an alternating structure. We corroborate this displacement via first principles calculations that predict that the fully eclipsed stacking (AA) is energetically unfavorable. The calculated stable arrangement of the layers exhibits a displacement of a 1.1 Å between the layers towards the b axis, imposing a slipped-parallel packing (AB) pattern on the structure, which is consistent with the experimental measure-

ments. This slipped-parallel stacking configuration is ~ 1 eV more stable than the eclipsed one. In the relaxed structure we performed a bond-length analysis in order to elucidate the oxidation character of the HOTP^{3-} ligand, because the C-O bond length could be indicative of the semiquinone oxidation state of the ligand unit [29]. We observed an average C-O bond length of 1.293 Å, which is indeed consistent with a semiquinone character for the HOTP^{3-} ligand [30].

FIG. 2. (a) DFT+U calculated spin density of two consecutive layers of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$. Color code: blue (red) spin up (spin down). Isosurface 0.009. (b) Magnetic exchange coupling calculated with different Hubbard U values. The experimental value of $J/k_B = 2$ K is matched for the combination $U(\text{Cu}) = 7.3$ eV and $U(\text{C}, \text{O}) = 4$ eV.

Our spin-polarized DFT+U calculations (see Methods) elucidate the magnetic properties of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$, confirming the $S = 1/2$ magnetic ground state. This is caused by the spin frustration arrangement of the magnetic moments of the Cu^{2+} atoms on the kagome lattice structure and antiferromagnetic interlayer coupling. Figure 2(a) reveals that the spin density of the system is mainly located in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the Cu^{II} atoms and in the σ O-Cu bonds of each ligand molecule. The contributions to the spin density are different, since 79% is present at each of the Cu^{II} atoms with the remainder on the ligand units (mainly located at the O atoms). Notice that the lack of spin density calculated for the HOTP^{3-} radical (for which an unpaired electron delocalized over the π -system is expected) may be in agreement with the structural features of the solid. In fact, for similar MOFs based on the THQ ligand (THQ = tetrahydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone) this lack of magnetism was attributed to strong

$\pi - \pi$ interactions between ligands of adjacent layers, stabilizing spin singlet dimers [30].

We followed a systematic broken symmetry approach to calculate the magnetic exchange coupling J , which can be estimated from the difference in energy of the possible spin configurations as $2J = E_{S=1/2} - E_{S=3/2}$. This broken symmetry method has been shown to generate accurate results for other trinuclear Cu systems [31–35]. In these calculations we explored the effect of using different Hubbard U values until we reached convergence with the experimental value of $J/k_B = 2$ K (Fig.2(b)).

The interplane exchange coupling was also investigated in the same way and was found to be smaller than the in-plane exchange coupling by around a factor of two and to be antiferromagnetic in character for the converged Hubbard parameters. Since the nearest-neighbour magnetic coordination is also twice as large for in-plane interactions as for inter-plane interactions, we expect the frustrated in-plane interactions to dominate the properties and suppress long-range magnetic order.

FIG. 3. (a) Calculated DFT+ U band structure of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ for the most stable slipped AB configuration. Color code: blue (red) spin up (spin down). Corresponding band structures for (b) the AA eclipsed configuration and (c) an isolated monolayer.

Experimentally $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ and similar kagome systems are shown to behave as semiconductors [27]. However, theory usually predicts a metallic ground state for this type of

FIG. 4. Atom contributions to the density of states for the stable slipped configuration, (a) close to the Fermi level and (b) over a wider energy range.

FIG. 5. Orbital contributions within the PDOS for (a) C atoms and (b) O atoms.

lattice [36]. Fig.3(a) shows the calculated band structure for $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ with the most stable slipped structure. A continuous band gap of ~ 0.25 eV is present on the plane of the layers (Γ -M-K) whereas a relatively wide dispersion is observed in the stacking direction (Γ -A-L-H), where a number of levels are crossing the Fermi energy. This indicates a strong

interaction between metal-organic sheets due the $\pi - \pi$ interactions between the aromatic rings presents in the structure, which is in good agreement with the interlayer distance obtained of ~ 3.15 Å. In order to elucidate the effect of this $\pi - \pi$ interaction on the band structure dispersion, we checked the atomic and orbital contributions on the projected density of states of the system. As it can be seen in Fig.4, the contribution to the states near the Fermi energy is mainly due to the C and O atoms present in the system. Since our assumption is that the interactions in the stacking direction cause the observed dispersion in the band structure, one would expect that the orbitals involved in this interaction should be the ones pointing towards the stacking direction, i.e. the p_z orbitals of C and O. This is exactly what is observed in Fig.5, where the p_z orbitals are the only orbitals that contribute to the DOS in this energy range. In order to further confirm the importance of p_z overlap for the interlayer band width, we computed the band structure for $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ but in an eclipsed configuration, where the layers are stacked perfectly one on top of one another (Fig.3(b)). Here we can see that the dispersion in the Γ -A-L-H direction has increased substantially, since this arrangement causes the maximum possible overlap between the p_z orbitals of the C and O atoms in the organic ligands.

Since the experimental results indicate a highly 2D semiconducting state, rather than a quasi-1D metallic state, there is clearly an inconsistency between theory and experiment. This issue has been widely discussed, reaching the conclusion that the role of defects in the arrangement of stacking units is likely to limit coherent interlayer transport and prevent large metallic conductance in this class of materials [37–39]. In the extreme limit, the system could be represented by non-interacting monolayers, with the corresponding band structure shown in Fig.3(c). This shows a small semiconducting energy gap comparable to that observed experimentally. We also note that, if the system had the previously suggested simple alternating layer structure, it would have an even number of spins in the unit cell, which would not be compatible with the observed QSL ground state.

Muon spin relaxation

We have previously used zero-field (ZF) and longitudinal-field (LF) μSR to study spin dynamics in a range of low-dimensional spin 1/2 quantum systems, e.g. Heisenberg AF spin chains [40, 41], spin ladders [42] and layered quantum spin liquids [43, 44]. In all of

FIG. 6. (a) Example muon spin relaxation data, showing ZF muon spin relaxation at 80 mK and 44 K and LF muon spin relaxation at 50 mK for fields of 5 mT and 1.25 T, where the relaxation is purely electronic in origin. (b,c) Muon spin relaxation rate versus B_{LF} compared for two different temperatures, one well below the exchange energy J and the other well above. The solid lines show fits to the 2D spin diffusion model of Eq.(2). The dotted lines show the best attempts at fitting to power laws, which provide a much poorer description of the data than the 2D diffusion fits.

these studies the first step is to use ZF measurements to confirm that magnetic ordering is suppressed and the second step is to use LF studies to probe the the shape of the spectral density function describing the distribution of the fluctuations versus frequency, with the probe frequency being proportional to the applied field.

Examples of ZF and LF μ SR data for $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ are shown in Fig.6(a). No evidence for magnetic ordering is found in our studies taken down to 50 mK, consistent with the 38 mK upper limit for ordering reported earlier [28]. The ZF relaxation shows primarily a Kubo-Toyabe form at all temperatures, reflecting a dominant contribution from static nuclear dipolar fields, along with a weak electronic contribution resulting from spin dynamics, which is present at all temperatures. Application of LF quenches the nuclear contribution to the relaxation, leaving just the electronic contribution, which has the slow Lorentzian form that is expected for fast electron spin dynamics. The electronic relaxation rate decreases with increasing field, reflecting the characteristic frequency-dependent spectral density of the spin dynamics. It can be seen that a significant relaxation can still be measured even for fields above 1 T, Fig.6(a), indicating the presence of a rapid form of spin dynamics that is not easily quenched by the field.

2D spin diffusion

For spins diffusing in a 2D layer, the spin autocorrelation function $S_{2D}(t)$ reflects a random walk process describing the propagating spin excitations that takes the form [45]

$$S_{2D}(t) = [\exp(-2D_{2D}t)I_0(2D_{2D}t)]^2, \quad (1)$$

where I_0 is a Bessel function and D_{2D} is the diffusion rate in the layer. The corresponding spectral density $J_{2D}(\omega)$ is then given by the Fourier transform of $S_{2D}(t)$. For an implanted muon probe linked to a spin site in the lattice via a contact hyperfine coupling A the muon spin relaxation rate is given by

$$\lambda(B) = \frac{A^2}{4} J_{2D}(\gamma_e B_{\text{LF}}), \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma_e/2\pi = 28.02 \text{ GHz T}^{-1}$ is the gyromagnetic ratio of the electron and B_{LF} is the magnetic field.

Example plots of the relaxation rate versus field are shown in Fig.6(b,c), along with fits to Eq.(2). The two parameters obtained from the fits are the 2D diffusion rate, D_{2D} , derived

FIG. 7. (a) Temperature dependence of the 2D spin diffusion rate, D_{2D} , spanning between the QSL and PM regimes. The solid line is a fit to Eq.(3). (b) Temperature dependence of the diffusive fraction. The hyperfine coupling A_0 has been derived from the high temperature PM regime where the excitations are fully diffusive. In the QSL regime the diffusive fraction is reduced to $2/3$, suggesting localization of $1/3$ of the excitations.

from the field scaling of the J_{2D} function and the effective value of A^2 derived from the amplitude scaling factor for λ , as described by Eq.(2). It can be seen from Fig.6(b,c) that the 2D diffusion model provides a good representation of the observed field dependence. In contrast, a power law field dependence associated with a 1D diffusion model [40, 41] is not

found to be compatible with the data.

Quantum to classical crossover

The T dependence of the fitted parameters obtained from the 2D diffusion model is shown in Fig.7. From Fig.7(a) it can be seen that the diffusion rate is almost constant in the QSL region where $T \ll J/k_B$ and increases by about a factor of three in the PM region where $T \gg J/k_B$. The T dependence can be fitted to the sum of a term with a weak power law n and an activated term reflecting the thermal excitation of singlets

$$D_{2D}(T) = D_0 T^n + D_1 \exp(-J/T). \quad (3)$$

The values obtained from this fit are $D_0 = 53(4) \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $n = 0.03(3)$, $D_1 = 103(11) \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $J/k_B = 2.6(4) \text{ K}$. The fitted J value is broadly comparable to that obtained from the susceptibility [28]. It is found that the value of D_0 closely matches $J/h = 54 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and D_1 closely matches $2D_0$. The crossover from the low- T quantum region to the high- T classical PM region is qualitatively similar to that recently observed in the triangular lattice QSL system YbZnGaO_4 [44]. However there are some notable differences in the scaling between the asymptotic values of D_{2D} and J/h . Here the QSL region is the one that closely matches J/h , whereas for YbZnGaO_4 it was the PM region that matched J/h . The ratio of D_{2D} values between PM and QSL regions is 3 in this case, whereas it was more than 10 for YbZnGaO_4 [44]. This contrasting behaviour may reflect the different underlying lattices and differences in the quantum entanglement lengths in the respective QSL phases. The quantum entanglement will be discussed in a later section.

Localized states

The normalised T dependence of the A^2 coupling factor in Eq.(2) is shown in Fig.7(b). In the paramagnetic region ($T \gg J/k_B$), the value of A is found to be $A_0 = 135(3) \text{ MHz}$, consistent with the size of hyperfine coupling expected in a muoniated molecular radical probe state formed on the ligand (see Methods). In the QSL region ($T \ll J/k_B$), the effective value of A^2 falls to around 2/3 of its high T value. We do not expect strong T dependence in A , so this drop in effective scaling factor is assigned to a reduced fraction of

diffusive excitations in the overall spectral density, i.e. $f_{\text{diff}} = A^2/A_0^2$. The low temperature missing fraction in the spectral density is assigned to a significant fraction of low frequency localized excitations $f_{\text{loc}} = 1 - f_{\text{diff}}$ that is suggested to emerge in the QSL region of Fig.7(b). The spectral region for finding these localised excitations is below 0.02 T. At 50 mK the low field relaxation can be modelled as the sum of the 2D diffusion term, obtained from fitting to the higher field data, and a Lorentzian term with a low-field cut-off. From the cut-off field, the characteristic fluctuation rate of the localized excitation is estimated to be around 80 MHz at 50 mK. As expected from the f_{loc} inferred from Fig.7(b), the low-field Lorentzian term is absent from the data at 10 K.

Quantum entanglement

The diffusion rate is related to the diffusion constant, D , the spinon velocity, v , momentum relaxation time, τ , and the hopping distance or mean free path, $l = v\tau$, via

$$D = \frac{1}{2}v^2\tau = \frac{1}{2}vl = D_{2\text{D}}l^2, \quad (4)$$

$$D_{2\text{D}} = \frac{v}{2l} = \frac{1}{2\tau}. \quad (5)$$

If the velocity is independent of T , as would be expected for a linear Dirac spinon dispersion or a spinon Fermi surface (FS) state, then $D_{2\text{D}}$ follows the inverse of the mean free path l . Whereas l is expected to match the nearest neighbour inter-site distance a in the classical region, in the QSL region quantum entanglement is expected to increase the length scale for the diffusion and l derived from Eq.(5) can be taken to give a measure of the entanglement length ξ_E [46]. Another way of quantifying the entanglement is to use the quantum Fisher information F_Q [47, 48], defined here in terms of the spectral density

$$F_Q = \frac{4}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \tanh^2 \left(\frac{\hbar\omega}{2k_{\text{B}}T} \right) J(\omega) d\omega, \quad (6)$$

which is shown in Fig.8(a). The high T behaviour is consistent with the predicted universal $T^{-3/4}$ form [47], whereas a weaker T -dependence is found for $T < J/k_{\text{B}}$. Since the number of locally entangled spins within a 2D layer can be taken to scale with F_Q , another estimate of the entanglement length is given by $F_Q^{1/2}$. The T -dependences of the normalised ξ_E values calculated via F_Q and $D_{2\text{D}}$ are compared in Fig.8(b). Both increase approximately threefold in the quantum region compared to the classical region. It is notable that the $D_{2\text{D}}$ -derived

FIG. 8. (a) The parameter F_Q derived from J_{2D} using Eq.6. The T -dependence in the high T region is consistent with the universal $T^{-0.75}$ power law for $N = 4$ entangled particles [47] (dashed line). (b) Entanglement length ξ_E normalised to ξ_0 (the value at 25 K). Estimates of this property as derived from F_Q and D_{2D} are compared.

value shows a more well-defined transition around J , whereas the value from F_Q changes more gradually.

FIG. 9. Types of spinon dispersion for 2D gapless QSL states. (a) Large area spinon FS and (b-d) band-touching states having (b) linear, (c) quadratic and (d) quartic dispersion.

Critical exponents and QSL models

The weak T -dependence of D_{2D} in the QSL region contrasts with the power law dependence reflecting quantum critical (QC) fluctuations that was recently found in D_{2D} for the triangular lattice QSL system 1T-TaS₂ [43]. This might be taken to indicate only weak QC fluctuations here. However the power law for the electronic specific heat in Cu₃(HOTP)₂ was recently reported to be $n_C = 0.52$ [28], which can be compared to the $2/3$ power law previously found for herbertsmithite [49]. This value suggests the presence of significant fluctuations, as it is substantially reduced from the expected value in the absence of such fluctuations, which would either be 1 for a spinon FS state or 2 for a Dirac QSL. A low temperature power law for the magnetic susceptibility was also reported as $n_\chi = -0.31$ for T in the range 0.04 to 0.3 K [28]. This differs from the expected value of 0 for a spinon FS without fluctuations. In the QC scenario, the power law versus T for the momentum relaxation time is $2/\nu - 3$ [50], where ν is the correlation length critical exponent. From Eq.(5) we expect the diffusion rate power law to be

$$n_D = 3 - 2/\nu. \quad (7)$$

For the first term in Eq.(3) that determines the D_{2D} dependence below 1 K in Fig.7(a), we obtained the relatively weak exponent $n_D = 0.03(3)$, leading to the estimate $\nu = 0.673(7)$. This is consistent with the value of 0.672 expected for the O(2) criticality class [51] and notably lower than the O(4) value of 0.748 [51] that was found to be consistent with both

n_D and n_C in the case of the triangular lattice QSL 1T-TaS₂ [43].

The predicted value for n_χ is

$$n_\chi = q - \gamma = q - (2 - \eta)\nu \quad (8)$$

where q is the power law for the density of states (DOS) versus energy and $\eta \sim 0.04$ [51]. The value of n_C depends on the critical exponent α , giving [43]

$$n_C = 1 + q - \alpha = q - 1 + 3\nu \quad (9)$$

where the second equality uses the scaling relation $\alpha = 2 - 3\nu$. From the reported value of n_C , the DOS parameter $q = -0.48(2)$ would be obtained from (9) under the assumption that the mobile spinons with $\nu = 0.673$ are also the main contributor to the specific heat.

TABLE I. QSL excitation models, with predicted parameters compared against experimental values of n_D from μ SR, n_χ from susceptibility and n_C from specific heat via Eqs.(7), (8) and (9). A spinon FS (line 1) is not a good overall fit with experiment (line 7), even with the inclusion of gauge fluctuations [44] (GF, line 2). Spinons with dispersion $q=-0.48$, close to the quartic value -0.5 , could match both exponents n_D and n_C (line 3), but the predicted n_χ would not be consistent with experiment. Spinons with quadratic dispersion (line 4) can be excluded, since their predicted n_C and n_χ values are both inconsistent with experiment. In contrast, linearly dispersing spinons are consistent with experiment for both n_D and n_χ (line 5). In this case the observed low value of n_C can be assigned to dominant singlet excitations with quadratic dispersion and ν close to the mean field value of 0.5 (line 6).

	q	ν	n_D	n_χ	n_C
1. Spinon (FS)	0		0	0	1
2. Spinon (FS+GF)	0		0.33		0.67
3. Spinon (quartic)	-0.48	0.67	0.03	-1.79	0.52
4. Spinon (quadratic)	0	0.67	0.03	-1.31	1.02
5. Spinon (linear)	1	0.67	0.03	-0.31	2.02
6. Singlet (quadratic)	0	0.51			0.52
7. Experiment			0.03	-0.31	0.52

Negative q indicates a large concentration of the DOS at low energies, falling away rapidly with increasing energy. The obtained q value is close to the value -0.5 associated with a quartic dispersion. The q value differs substantially from $q = 1$ for a linear Dirac spinon dispersion or $q = 0$ for a quadratic spinon dispersion or a large area FS state (Fig.9). However a quartic spinon state can be excluded, since it would have a large negative n_χ , which is not consistent with experiment.

The properties of various QSL excitation models are compared with the measured exponents in Table I. As we have noted, spinon FS and quartic spinon models give a poor match with experiment. A quadratic spinon dispersion can also be excluded, since both n_C and n_χ are inconsistent with experiment. In contrast, linear spinon dispersion is much more promising, since both n_D and n_χ are matching with experiment. The predicted n_C in this case is close to 2, which is much larger than the experimental value. However, we note that in practice such a large non-phonon exponent would be masked by the phonon contribution with a similarly large exponent [28]. It would then be consistent with the experimental data to assign the observed n_D and n_χ to spinons with linear dispersion, if the observed low value of n_C can be assigned to another type of excitation that dominates the low temperature specific heat. A natural assignment for this would be the singlet excitations of a QSL, that do not contribute to the spin transport or magnetic susceptibility. If these singlets have the same ν value as the spinons, then q must be negative, as discussed earlier. Alternatively a simple quadratic dispersion model for the singlets can be assumed, leading to a ν value close to the mean field value of 0.5 (Table I, line 6), which would seem to be a more reasonable assignment. One plausible interpretation for these singlets is that they are the vison vortices that would be associated with a Z_2 QSL [1, 50, 52]. Following these considerations, our best assignments of excitation against experiment are shown in bold in Table I.

In summary, from these results it can be seen that MOF-based kagome systems have some clear advantages over purely inorganic-based systems such as herbertsmithite in allowing us to measure the intrinsic properties of the frustrated $S=1/2$ spins on the kagome lattice. The main advantage is that there are no inter-layer sites for the transition metal ions that could act as localized defect spins and obscure the intrinsic properties. Another beneficial factor here is that the moderate J value provides a convenient energy scale that allows experiments to easily span between the quantum and classical regimes. This has allowed the intrinsic magnetic properties of the ideal kagome QSL and its entanglement properties to be

elucidated more clearly than was possible in previously studied inorganic kagome systems having larger J .

The present system has been found to be effectively gapless, with the upper limit to the gap being of order $0.02 J$. Different QSL models were compared against the experimental data and it was found that a large area spinon FS model is not compatible with experiment. QSL models with quadratic or quartic dispersion were also found to be at variance with experiment, whereas a Z_2 -linear Dirac QSL with both spinon and vison excitations was shown to be fully consistent with μ SR, magnetic susceptibility and specific heat data.

METHODS

Electronic structure

We performed first principles spin-polarized density functional theory (DFT) calculations in the plane wave formalism as implemented in the Quantum ESPRESSO package [53]. The exchange-correlation energy is calculated using the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional [54]. We selected standard solid-state pseudopotentials from the Materials Cloud database [55]. The strong correlations of the d electrons of the Cu ions of Cu_3HOTP_2 were considered by implementing the Hubbard-corrected DFT+U approach, choosing a standard on-site Hubbard U of 7.3 eV for the Cu atoms and 4 eV for C and O atoms in the simplified version proposed by Dudarev et al [56]. The electronic wave functions were expanded with well-converged kinetic energy cut-offs for the wave functions and charge density of 60 and 480 eV, respectively. The chemical structure of the bulk was fully optimized using the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) algorithm until the forces on each atom were smaller than 5×10^{-3} Ry/au and the energy difference between two consecutive relaxation steps was less than 1×10^{-4} Ry. We relaxed the molecular structure and the lattice parameters conserving the hexagonal lattice symmetry. Dispersion corrections were considered by applying semi-empirical Grimme-D2 corrections [57]. The Brillouin zone was sampled by a fine Γ -centered $3 \times 3 \times 12$ k -point Monkhorst–Pack mesh [58] for SCF calculations and $6 \times 6 \times 16$ for NSCF calculations.

Muon spectroscopy

Samples for the muon studies of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HOTP})_2$ that are reported here were prepared using the method of Hmadeh et al. [24]. The muon measurements [59] were carried out using the HiFi spectrometer at the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source. A helium dilution refrigerator provided sample temperatures down to 50 mK. The sample was 300 mg of powder mounted in a thin silver foil packet clamped onto a silver sample plate. Some measurements were initially made in zero field to confirm the absence of magnetic ordering at low temperatures, but the bulk of the measurements were made in longitudinal field to provide information about the spin dynamics. These LF measurements were made in fields supplied by the HiFi superconducting magnet, covering a range between 5 mT and 2.5 T. Each individual measurement collected 3×10^7 positron events resulting from the decay of the positive muons implanted into the sample. The data set is available from the ISIS Facility [60].

The hyperfine coupling expected for muon addition to the ligand was estimated by taking the molecule 1,2-dioxyphenylene as a simple model to represent one third of the HOTP molecule. For muonium addition to site 3 of this molecule we obtain a hyperfine coupling of 135 MHz from DFT using the Gaussian16 code [61] at the level of B3LYP/cc-pVDZ. This value has been corrected for quantum enhancement by calibration against the hyperfine coupling for the muoniated radical in benzene. The bare value before quantum correction was 110 MHz.

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Author contributions: EC conceived the project, VGL and MCL prepared and char-

acterised the sample, FLP took the muon data, analysed the results and prepared the first draft of the paper, DLA carried out the DFT calculations supervised by JJB and reported the results. All authors reviewed and refined the manuscript.

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Data and material availability: The muon raw data files are available via the identifier code DOI:10.5286/ISIS.E.RB2010775. Other parts of the data are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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